

AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

PRODUCTIVITY OF SPRING BARLEY IN THE SOUTHERN FOREST-STEPPE OF WESTERN SIBERIA

Timokhin A.,
Boiko V.

Omsk agrarian scientific center, Russian Federation
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Abstract

The studies were carried out in the southern forest-steppe of Western Siberia (Omsk region, Omsk district). Studies have shown that the combination of protective measures in agricultural technology and a moderate level of chemicalization (N30-60P60) makes it possible to realize the high biological potential of the main grain forage crop in Siberian crop production.

Keywords: spring barley, productivity, soil, agrocenosis.

Among cereals, spring barley is one of the earliest ripening, most drought-resistant and salt-tolerant crops. Further growth in the production of barley grain is impossible on the basis of extensive factors, it is required to increase the yield through the fullest possible use of the potential of varieties. Relatively high yields and lower demands on growing conditions determine the demand for this crop in the agricultural production of the region [1, 2]. In the current economic conditions, the main direction of development of crop production in Russia is associated with the conservation of resources and energy, environmental safety and high profitability of production. In a changing climate, high-yielding varieties are created with improved food and fodder qualities and a minimal response to unfavorable biotic and abiotic environmental factors [3, 4].

Barley grain is an indispensable raw material for brewing, it is used in the flour-grinding and confectionery industries, cereals are produced from it, but its main purpose is feed [5, 6]. In the diet of feeding animals and

birds, barley grain is the main and indispensable ingredient, which is of paramount importance for saturating the feed with vegetable protein [7, 8].

The studies were carried out in 2018-2019, in an eight-field crop rotation of the laboratory of field forage production of the Federal State Budgetary Scientific Institution "Omsk ASC", founded in 1978. The purpose of the research is to identify the response of spring barley variety Omsky 99 to different levels of mineral nutrition (accounting plot area - 36 m², 3-fold repetition).

The scheme of the three-factor experiment included the following factors: different availability of mobile phosphorus (according to Chirikov) - medium (0), increased (I and II), high (III); options for applying nitrogen (N60 and N30) and phosphate fertilizers (P60) and without them. This made it possible to simulate different conditions of nitrogen-phosphorus nutrition, in comparison with the control (without fertilizers) (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 - General scheme of experiments

The soil of the plot is meadow-chernozem, heavy loamy, medium thick, medium humus. The initial content of nitrate nitrogen is low, mobile phosphorus and potassium (according to Chirikov) in the control variant are medium and high, respectively. The occurrence of groundwater in autumn is on average at the level of 3 m.

Autumn tillage - non-moldboard to a depth of 15 cm. Closing of moisture in the spring against autumn backgrounds. Cultivation before sowing.

Phosphorus-containing fertilizers (ammophos, P60) and nitrogen fertilizers (ammonium nitrate - N30-60) were applied in the appropriate variants for pre-sowing cultivation.

The seeding rate of barley is 5.5 million units/ha. Sowing of barley was carried out in the third decade of May.

The remaining agrotechnical practices are recommended for zonal soils of the southern forest-steppe.

Variety of spring barley Omsk 99 selection FSBSI "Omsk Agrarian Scientific Center". This variety belongs to the forest-steppe ecological group, drought-resistant, mid-season, the growing season is 78-90 days. Over the years of study on an artificial infectious background, he showed a weak susceptibility to black and dusty smut, and is practically resistant to stone smut.

In terms of productivity, the variety belongs to the high-yielding varieties in the conditions of Western Siberia. The maximum yield was obtained in 2011 in a competitive variety trial - 5.03 t/ha, the increase to the standard was +0.66 t/ha.

The dynamics of total moisture in the meadow-chernozem soil in the southern forest-steppe zone shows that the moisture content during the growing season of spring barley in 2018 and 2019 was in the range from capillary rupture moisture (CRM) to the lowest moisture capacity (LMC). In this interval, it is most accessible to plants, which provides normal conditions for the growth and development of culture (рис. 2).

Fig. 2 - Dynamics of total moisture in the soil in a meter layer.

Barley with a spring grain yield reacted to different levels of nitrogen-phosphorus nutrition. A significant increase in yield was ensured both by the pre-sowing application of phosphorus-containing fertilizers and the aftereffect of previously created backgrounds with

different phosphorus availability. On average, pre-sowing application of P60 increased the yield by 0.92 t/ha or 30%, with a higher increase - 1.40 t/ha or 67% against the background with an average phosphorus content (Table 1).

Table 1

Grain yield of spring barley depending on the conditions of mineral nutrition, t/ha, 2018-2019

Dose of mineral fertilizers, kg of active substance per hectare	Phosphorus content in soil				Averages
	0	I	II	III	
N0	2,04	2,70	3,33	3,38	2,86
N30	2,17	2,76	3,36	3,48	2,94
N60	2,07	3,18	3,79	4,01	3,26
P60N0	3,29	3,71	4,30	3,73	3,76
P60N30	3,81	3,70	4,34	4,16	4,00
P60N60	3,38	4,04	4,26	4,56	4,06
Averages	2,79	3,35	3,90	3,89	

Least significant difference for partial means – 0,71

The aftereffect of backgrounds with high and high content of mobile phosphorus in the soil contributed to an increase in the harvest of spring barley grain to 3.35-3.89 t/ha at 2.79 t/ha against a natural background in terms of phosphorus content.

Nitrogen fertilizers on barley are less effective, possibly due to sowing after the leguminous crop, but a significant increase of 0.35 t/ha or 11% was ensured by the introduction of N60. The combination of the studied factors increased the yield from 2.04 to 4.56 t/ha, or 2.2 times.

The combination of protective measures in agricultural technology and a moderate level of chemicalization (N30-60P60) makes it possible to realize the high biological potential of the main grain forage crop in Siberian crop production.

References:

1. Boiko, V. S. Spring barley in irrigated agricultural cenosis of forest-steppe of Western Siberia / V. S. Boiko, A. Y. Timokhin, T. M. Khaseinov // *Zemledeleie*. – 2016. – N 3. – P. 35-37.
2. Spring barley as perspective culture of rice crop rotations in Kalmykia / N. N. Dubenok, V. V. Kuznetsova, V. V. Borodychev, S. B. Adyaev // *Proceedings of Lower Volga Agro-University Complex: Science and Higher Education*. – 2014. – No 1(33). – P. 18-22.
3. Kamalihin, V. E. Agro economic assessment of spring barley cultivation technology / V. E. Kamalihin, V. I. Kargin, N. N. Neyaskin // *Journal of Advanced Research in Dynamical and Control Systems*. – 2020. – Vol. 12. – No S4. – P. 1255-1258. – DOI 10.5373/JARDCS/V12SP4/20201601.
4. The productivity of spring barley when using cobalt nanoparticles and liquid-phase biological product / T. Seregina, O. Chernikova, Y. Mazhaysky, L. Ampleeva // *Agronomy Research*. – 2021. – Vol. 19. – No 4. – P. 1962-1969. – DOI 10.15159/AR.21.121.
5. Kurbanov, R. K. Determination of Spring Barley Lodging Area with Help of Unmanned Aerial Vehicle / R. K. Kurbanov, N. I. Zakharova // *Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies*. – 2022. – Vol. 245. – P. 247-257. – DOI 10.1007/978-981-16-3349-2_21.
6. Spring barley performance benefits from simultaneous shallow straw incorporation and top dressing as revealed by rhizotrons with resealable sampling ports / R. Reichel, Z. Li, N. Brüggemann [et al.] // *Biology and Fertility of Soils*. – 2022. – DOI 10.1007/s00374-022-01624-1.
7. Significance of spring barley variety in energy-saving cultivation technologies / V. V. Glukhovtsev, S. Y. Zarevskiy, E. V. Stolpivskaya [et al.] // *Russian Agricultural Sciences*. – 2012. – Vol. 38. – No 4. – P. 259-261.
8. Boiko, V. S. Change in the Phosphate Status of Western Siberian Forest-Steppe Soils through the Continuous Use of Fertilizers / V. S. Boiko, A. Y. Timokhin, V. N. Yakimenko // *Russian Agricultural Science*. – 2021. Vol. 47. – P. 132-137. DOI 10.3103/S1068367421020038